

Lighting in Ankia Bhaona: From Early Times to Contemporary Practices

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Abstract

Ankia Bhaona, a traditional Assamese theatrical form created by the 15th-century Sankaradeva, is a vibrant blend of art, spirituality, and community engagement. Central to its night-time performances in pre-modern Assam was the ingenious use of traditional lighting techniques, which not only illuminated the stage but also carried philosophical symbolic meanings. This paper explores the diverse lighting methods employed in Ankia Bhaona, including Aariya, Agnigarh, Choutara, Bhotachaki, Matir chaki (Earthen lamps), Fuljhari, Mota or Mahota, Phirfiri, Tota, Chengeli and Chakraban. Drawing from historical texts, cultural practices, and symbolic interpretations, the study examines the materials, preparation methods, and socio-spiritual roles of these lighting systems.

Keywords: Sankardeva, Ankia Bhaona, traditional lighting, Modern Lighting,

1.0 Introduction

Ankia Bhaona is more than just a dramatic performance; its way to show Assam's Vaishnavite faith, a devotion to Lord Vishnu through music, dance, and drama, Introduced by Sankardeva in fifteen and sixteen centuries. This art form communicates religious narratives mainly drawn from texts like the Bhagavata Purana, Harivamsa, Vishnu Purana, and

Ramayana. Lighting played a critical role in these performances, particularly as they were often held at night to accommodate rural audiences. Unlike modern theatre, which relies on electric lighting, Ankia Bhaona performances in medieval Assam depended on indigenous lighting techniques to create a visually and spiritually captivating experience. These methods, rooted in locally available materials and traditional knowledge, were both functional and symbolic, embodying the spiritual ethos of the performance. The absence of electricity in pre-modern Assam necessitated innovative solutions to illuminate night-time performances. Materials such as bamboo, mustard oil, sulphur, iron powder etc. were ingeniously combined to produce light sources that varied in intensity, colour, and effect. These lighting systems—*Aariya*, *Agnigarh*, *Choutara*, *Bhotachaki*, *Matir Chaki*, *Dola Chaki*, *Fuljhari*, *Mota or Mahota*, *Phirfiri*, *Tota*, *Chengeli* and *chakraban* etc. served practical purposes while reinforcing the devotional and aesthetic dimensions of Ankia Bhaona. This paper aims to provide a comprehensive analysis of these techniques, exploring their preparation, use, and symbolic meaning.

1.01 Aims and Objectives

1.01.1 Aim:

Aim to explore the evolution of lighting techniques in Ankia Bhaona, from traditional methods rooted in spiritual representation to contemporary practices influenced by modern technology.

1.01.2 Objectives:

- To document and analyse traditional lighting methods used in Ankia Bhaona performances.
- Identifying the symbolic and spiritual significance of traditional lighting techniques in Ankia Bhaona
- To explore the changeover from traditional to modern lighting practices in Ankia Bhaona.

- To evaluate the impression of modern lighting on the aesthetic and spiritual dimensions of Ankia Bhaona.
- To propose recommendations for integrating traditional symbolism with modern lighting technologies.

1.02 Significance of the Study

This study is significant not only for its contribution to Assamese cultural historiography but also for its broader implications in the fields of theatre studies, performance technology, and heritage preservation. By exploring how lighting functioned both as a practical tool and a symbolically loaded ritual element, the paper highlights an often-overlooked dimension of Sankardev's theatrical vision. The study also emphasizes the need for preserving traditional knowledge systems in the face of rapid technological modernity. For practitioners, historians, and cultural theorists, this research offers a detailed framework to re-evaluate the balance between innovation and tradition in sacred and folk theatre forms.

1.03 Review of Literature

There has been a lot of research work done on lighting system in theatre; a good number of books have been published but no research work has been done extensively in detail using light in Ankia Bhaona. Few articles and books provide insights into the historical and traditional use of lighting in Ankia Bhaona. Hemanta Kumar Sarma's article, "*Bhaonat Prasin Alok Byvosthaaru Agnigrah*", published in *Natya-Prasang* (edited by Ramsaran Thakuria and Dayanand Pathak), offers valuable information on ancient lighting practices in Ankia Bhaona. Similarly, *Guru Charit* by Ram Charan Thakur includes explanations of lighting systems used in Ankia Bhaona performances. Keshvananda Dev Goswami's book "*Ankia Bhaona*" briefly discusses the creation and use of lighting in these performances. Srihorichandra Bhattacharya's "*Axomiya Natya Sahityar Jilingoni*" and Utpal Narayan Goswami's "*Bhaonar Purbaranga: Vaividhyaaru Vaicitrya* (Dissertation, M.Phil, Guwahati University)," also provide some details on traditional lighting techniques. Notably, no comprehensive research or dedicated works exist

on lighting systems in contemporary Bhaona performances, indicating a significant gap in this area. Modern theatre, particularly in the global context, has seen extensive research on lighting systems, with numerous books published in English. Notable works include G.N. Dasgupta's "Guide to Stage Lighting", Neil Fraser's "Stage Lighting Explained and Stage Lighting Design" etc. These texts provide detailed insights into the technical and artistic aspects of stage lighting but. in the Assamese context, however, research remains sparse. Nand Kishore Maheshwari's "Natakar Kichu Katha" offers some discussion on lighting design, while "Natak aru Mancha", edited by Pankaj Kumar Dutta, includes Dulal Bhattacharya's essay on the necessity of stage lighting. Additionally, in "Rangamancha Alochana", edited by Promod Chandra Medhi, Kalyan De and Manik Ahmed contribute two essays: "Natakt Poharar Prayojaniyata aru Iyar Prayog Naipunyata" and "Adhunik Natakata Poharar Bhumika". Despite these contributions, no dedicated books on stage lighting exist in Assamese, highlighting a need for further research in this domain. In summary, while Ankia Bhaona's lighting systems are briefly addressed in a few Assamese texts, detailed studies are absent, especially for contemporary performances. Modern theatre, globally, benefits from extensive literature, but in Assam, the discourse remains limited to a few essays, underscoring a significant research gap in both traditional and modern Assamese theatre lighting.

1.04 Research gap

Although scholars have explored Sankardev's scriptural innovations, musicality, dramaturgy, and language, limited academic attention has been paid to one of the most integral yet ignored aspects of performance—lighting. This paper researches the lighting techniques used in Ankia Bhaona from a historical perspective and critically evaluates the shifts brought about by modern technologies and aesthetic sensibilities.

1.05 Methodology

This study applies qualitative research approach, combining historical analysis with ethnographic methods:

- Examination of historical texts to understand traditional lighting practices and their symbolic meanings.
- Attending contemporary Ankia Bhaona performances to observe contemporary lighting practices.
- Conducting interviews with performers, lighting technicians, and scholars to gain perceptions into both traditional and modern lighting techniques.
- Comparing traditional and modern lighting methods to evaluate their impact on the performance's aesthetic and spiritual dimensions

1.06 Research Design

The research is designed as a historical-comparative study with a dual focus: (1) documentation and analysis of traditional lighting forms, and (2) critical evaluation of the changes brought by contemporary lighting systems. The first phase involves archival and field-based exploration of indigenous techniques, while the second phase compares these with lighting developments post-colonial contact and into the current proscenium era.

1.07 Sample

Data was collected from a purposive sample consisting of:

- Bhaona practitioners and experts from different part of Assam.
- Artists involved in preparing traditional lighting tools.
- Lighting designers and cultural historians associated with Assamese theatre.

The sample was selected for their experiential knowledge and geographical relevance to the research topic.

1.08 Data Collection

Data collection methods included:

- Semi-structured interviews with performers and artisans.
- Direct observation of performances at Sattras, Namghars and community festivals.
- Visual documentation and photography of lighting devices.
- Textual analysis of historical literature and Bhaona manuals.

1.09 Data Analysis

Thematic analysis was used to identify symbolic patterns, functional characteristics, and technological processes in traditional lighting. Comparative analysis was employed to understand the divergence between earlier and contemporary practices. The data was then synthesized to draw connections between form, function, and philosophical meanings embedded in lighting choices.

2.0 Purposes of Lighting in Theatre: A Theoretical Overview

In staging a successful drama, lighting plays an important role. This is because light is a primary and integral element of drama. With the help of lights, many incredible and imaginative scenes are presented on stage, entertaining audiences. Lighting not only transforms the subject matter but also gives tangible form to the stage's scenic design and contributes to the expression of the performance. In drama, the complexities of the subconscious mind, people from different classes, diverse attitudes, varied reactions to the same event, and more are vividly portrayed to the audience through lighting.

To situate the discussion in a broader theatrical context, it is essential to understand the accepted functions of lighting in theatre:

- Proper lighting highlights the primary character or action and confirms clarity.
- Through intensity, colour, and shadow, lighting sets the emotional tone.
- Lighting can indicate the time of day, location, or shift in dimensions.

- Emotional or psychological states of characters can be portrayed through lighting.
- Colours and light patterns can symbolically represent ideas or transitions.
- Changes in lighting help signal transitions between scenes or acts.ⁱ

3.0 Lighting in Early Ankia Bhaona

Contemporary theatre, which depend on electric lighting, Ankia Bhaona performances in medieval Assam depended on indigenous lighting techniques to create a visually and spiritually captivating experience. These methods, rooted in locally available materials and traditional knowledge, were both functional and symbolic, embodying the spiritual ethos of the performance. The absence of electricity in pre-modern Assam necessitated innovative solutions to illuminate night-time performances. Materials such as bamboo, mustard oil, Sulphur, and iron powder were ingeniously combined to produce light sources that varied in intensity, colour, and effect. These lighting systems—*Aariya*, *Agnigarh*, *choutara*, *Bhotachaki*, *Matir Chaki* (Earthen lamps), *Fuljhari*, *Mota or Mahata*, *Phirfiri*, *Tota*, and *Chakraban* etc. served practical purposes while emphasizing the devotional and aesthetic dimensions of Ankia Bhaona. This paper aims to provide a comprehensive analysis of these techniques, exploring their preparation, use, and cultural significance.

Historical records, oral narratives, and literary sources such as *Katha Gurucharita* suggest that Sankardev and his successors employed basic but effective lighting systems. These methods, though technologically simple, were infused with symbolic, spiritual, and theatrical significance.

3.01 Aariya

The Aariya, as defined in the *Hemkosha* dictionary, is a bundle of torn cloth tied to a bamboo stick, typically three meters long, and ignited to produce light.ⁱⁱ The cloth, often soaked in mustard or castor oil, is wrapped around the bamboo's end to form a *Jumuthi* (large bundle), the size of which determines the flame's intensity. In some variations, coconut oils or

firecrackers were incorporated to enhance the light output. The bamboo stick's length ensured durability, allowing the Aariya to burn steadily throughout the performance. Two individuals, known as *Aariya dhora* (Aariya holders), held the burning sticks upright, moving in rhythm with the music. Their synchronized dance highlighted the musicians and actors, ensuring visibility in the absence of modern stage lighting. The Aariya was strategically placed at the stage's corners or held in front of actors to illuminate their faces, particularly when they wore masks, a common feature in Bhaona. The Aariya's dual flames symbolized the twin paths of *shravan* (listening to divine teachings) and *kirtan* (singing praises), core tenets of Vaishnavism.ⁱⁱⁱ In the purbaranga (preliminary rituals), the Aariya was considered the first invocation of light, with the holders embodying Vishnu's *Nara-Narayana* forms, representing divine duality and devotion. Also, beyond just projecting light, Aariya signifies knowledge, science, and mystery. The term Aariya is likely derived from the Sanskrit word *Andika* (torch),^{iv} indicating its ritual and symbolic origins.

3.02 Bhotachaki

The *Bhotachaki* was a large, round vessel surrounded by candles or wicks, tied to poles at various points in the performance space. Alternatively, it was crafted from a bottom of banana tree, carved into a bowl shape, filled with mustard oil, and lit with wicks. Its glow was compared to a *Bhota Tara* (bright star), hence the name. It was strategically placed to illuminate key areas of the performance space, ensuring visibility for both performers and spectators. The *Bhotachaki* was considered a sacred symbol, often associated with Brahma, the creator. The act of pouring mustard oil into the *Bhotachaki* was deemed a pious ritual, reinforcing its spiritual importance in the Bhaona context.^v

3.03 Dola Chaki

Several large *Matir chakis* (earthen lamp) are placed around the *Dola* (Platter), each lamp is filled with mustard oil and fitted with strong wicks. Then, the wicks are lit and the *Dola* is hung in a high place to provide lighting for the performance space.^{vi}

3.04 Choutara

Choutara is a kind of large light-flame. A metal or clay vessel, filled with mustard oil and lined with wicks. Its light spreads far and wide. It is called *Choutara* because it shines all around like a star.^{vii}

3.05 Phirphiri

Phirphiri was used to arrange lighting on the stage. It was made with fine iron wires. A type of firecracker prepared in bamboo tubes was also called *Phirphiri*. It's produced a fiery spark.^{viii}

3.06 Mota or Mahata

The *Mota* or *Mahata* was a large, expensive, and less frequently used torch with a blue flame. It was primarily used to light the area just before an actor made their entrance. The colour blue, symbolizing divinity, elevated the metaphysical ambiance of Bhaona.^{ix} *The Mota or Mahata* was a costly lighting method involving a mixture of *Haital* (arsenic sesquisulphide,) 2 tola, (1 tola= 11.66 gram) *Jakhar* (saltpeter) 2 tola, ash from burnt bottle gourd 2 tola, and iron powder 0.5 tola. The mixture was ground, dried, and ignited on a bamboo stick during performances.^x

3.07 Agnigarh

The *Agnigarh* (fire structure) was a ritualistic lighting apparatus constructed to the west of the namghar. Made from thin planks of wood shaped like a bow, it was coated with *Hengul* (vermilion) and *Haital* (yellow arsenic). The structure featured nine holes—one central and four on each side—into which oil-soaked cotton wicks were inserted and lit. *Agnigarh* lit before the performance. Actors enter the stage through the base of the *Agnigarh*, a practice believed to purify the performance and introduce the performers. The structure's triangular or arched shape, supported by bamboo or wood, created a visually striking focal point. "In *Agnigarh*, it is necessary to light 9 or 12 wicks, and there is no objection if more are used, but fewer will not do. The nine wicks symbolize the nine forms of devotion (Navavidha Bhakti), and the twelve wicks represent the twelve sections of the Bhagavata Purana.^{xi}

3.08 Fuljhari

Fuljhari, a firework resembling a fountain,^{xii} was a spectacular lighting element used before the main Bhaona event. It was made by grinding and drying *Jakhar* (saltpeter) 6tola (1 tola = 11.66 gram), 1.5tola, of the resin of *Bahak tree*(Tultul Kutum), *Gandhak* (sulphur) 3tola, 1.5tola, of the resin of *Akand tree*(*Calotropis gigantea*) and iron powder 2.5tola. First the resin is dissolved in lemon juice, meaning it is soaked and then dried again.^{xiii} The preparation required expertise to ensure successful ignition.

The Fuljhari was buried with its hole upward and ignited, creating a dazzling display of sparks. Its use before the *Purbaranga* and marked the transition to the main performance, captivating the audience and setting a festive tone. It was believed that lighting this illuminated the *Boykuntha* (paradise of Lord Vishnu)^{xiv}

3.09 Tota

The *Tota* was prepared by burning bottle gourd shells ash, mixed with iron powder, *Jakhar*(saltpeter), *Gandhak*(Sulphur), and *Haital*, then wrapped in jackfruit leaves and bound with torn clothes. It burned brightly with sound, adding drama to the performance. *Tota* is a lighting system that burns with a sound.^{xv}

3.10 Chengeli

The *Chengeli* emits sparkling light. When a wick inserted into the small hole of the *Chengeli* and ignited. The following ingredients are needed to prepare the *Chengeli* - *Jakhar* 8 tola, *Gandhak* 1 tola, and a half a tola burnt powder from *Bhekuritree* (TultulKutum). When a sparkier is inserted into the small hole of *Chengeli* and lit, a light like that of a firecracker emerges from it.^{xvi}

3.11 Chakraban

Chakraban rotates like a wheel. It is associated with *Chengeli*. *Chakrabana* created with the help of two *Chengeli*. When the two *Chengelis* attached to the wick are lit, the wheel spin

with the petals and sparks of light scatter it like fireflies. The following ingredients are needed to prepare the *Chakraban Jakhar* 7 tola, *Gandhak* 2 tola, and a half a tola ashes from *Akand* (*Calotropis gigantea*) tree, 1.5 tola, of the resin of *Bahak tree* (Tultul Kutum), and one pound of iron powder.^{xvii}

3.12 Matir Chaki

Matir Chaki (Earthen lamp) was also used for lighting in performances. Generally, a large *Matir Chaki* was filled with mustard oil and a thick wick was lit and placed in a tall pole. Sometimes thousand lamps were used to provide lighting.^{xviii}

These were the lights mostly used in earlier period to staged Ankia Bhaona. These lights not only provided illumination but also aimed to bind the common audience with a sense of spirituality, enabling them to realise the ultimate truth of purity.

4.0 Transition and Western Influence: Colonial Period to Early Modernity

With the change of time, there has been a radical transformation in the field of theatre lighting systems as well. Artificial lighting systems have replaced natural lighting systems. This impact has also been felt in India. With the advent of British colonial rule, Indian drama underwent dramatic transformations. Western theatrical traditions, particularly Shakespearean structures, began to influence indigenous performance styles. Stagecraft—including the use of elaborate backdrops and artificial lighting—began to be adopted. The use of artificial lighting on Indian stages began during British rule with gas lights. Electric lighting in Indian theatre began in the last decade of the 19th century, but systematic light control had not yet been implemented. Coloured polythene was used on electric bulbs to create different coloured lights, and dimmers were operated by submerging electric wires in water-filled buckets or similar containers. The first person to introduce modern lighting control in Indian theatre was the late Satu Sen. He brought modern lighting techniques from America and initiated a new era of stage lighting in India. On August 8, 1931, at Kolkata's Rangmahal stage, Satu Sen applied modern lighting systematically in the play *Bishnupriya*, paving the way for advanced lighting control^{xix}.

In the late 1950s, internationally renowned lighting director Tapas Sen revolutionized stage lighting with a scientific and innovative approach, making lighting indispensable to theatre^{xx}. In contemporary times, for theatre lighting systems new lighting technologies such as digital lights LED lights, electronic dimmers and power consoles have been developed for theatre lighting systems. In today's era, directors and lighting artists have found it easier to stage plays through various experiments. Moreover, the ability to pre-program which colour light will be used in specific scenes has enabled directors to manage lighting according to their convenience. Additionally, atmospheres and various effects can be created in a very short time. As a result, the quality of plays has improved and audience can enjoy the experience without any inconvenience.

Assam too witnessed this shift. The introduction of the proscenium stage brought about changes in set design and technical apparatus. Gradually, Bhaona performances—especially those outside Sattras—began experimenting with kerosene lanterns and later electric bulbs. These changes were pragmatic and adapted to evolving audiences but gradually diluted the ritualistic simplicity of Sankardev's vision. In contemporary times, especially in performances categorized as *Matri Bhasha Bhaona*, the lighting design has undergone significant transformations. The use of artificial lights, and colour filters has become commonplace. While this reflects an attempt to modernize and attract new audiences, but it shows some certain contradictions are emerge parallelly.

5.0 Findings

Traditional Lighting Techniques:

Traditional lighting methods in Ankia Bhaona were deeply symbolic. For instance:

- Aariya: Represented the twin paths of shraavan (listening) and kirtan (singing), core tenets of Vaishnavism. Also, Aariya signifies knowledge, science, and mystery.
- Agnigarh: Symbolized the nine forms of devotion (Navavidha Bhakti) through its nine wicks.

- Bhotachaki: Associated with Brahma, the creator, and considered a sacred symbol.

These methods used locally available materials and were integral to the performance's spiritual ambiance.

6.0 Transition to Modern Lighting:

With the introduction of electric lighting, there has been a shift towards more visually striking but less symbolically rich lighting methods. Modern lighting often emphasizes spectacle over spirituality, leading to:

6.01 Over-illumination and Spectacle

Modern lighting setups often overwhelm the performance with intense brightness and rapid colour changes. So, it seems that the subtle interplay between shadow and narrative gets lost. Rather than enhancing the thematic depth, lighting becomes a spectacle, detracting from the devotional core.

6.02 Disconnection from Symbolic Frameworks

In traditional Bhaona, lighting was a ritual act with symbolic resonance. Modern lighting often lacks such symbolic embeddedness. Without a theological or dramaturgical rationale, lighting becomes arbitrary.

6.03 Technical Misunderstanding of Lighting Objectives

It seems that most modern productions fail to employ lighting as a narrative device. Instead of directing the audience's focus, establishing mood, or marking temporal shifts, lighting is used decoratively. This stems from a lack of trained lighting designers aware of the spiritual and dramaturgical frameworks of Bhaona.

7.0 Recommendations for Integrating Tradition with Innovation

Hence, it is an impractical stance for return to the traditional lighting system. Instead, a balance must be sought between innovation and authenticity.

- Culturally-Informed Lighting Design: Lighting designers must be trained not just in technical aspects but also in the philosophical and aesthetic principles of Bhaona.
- Minimalism over Maximalism: Controlled, narrative-driven use of lighting can enhance rather than disrupt.
- Use of Warm Light Tones: Mimicking traditional oil lamps through warmer colour
- temperatures can preserve the spiritual mood.

8.0 Conclusion

Ankia Bhaona is a timeless tradition whose spiritual, aesthetic, and philosophical dimensions remain unparalleled. Lighting, though often relegated to a secondary status, plays a critical role in shaping the audience's perceptual and emotional experience. Traditional methods—though simple—embodied deep symbolic and spiritual functions.

Modern transformations, while inevitable and in many cases welcome, must not stray from the core purpose of Sankardev's vision: the spiritual elevation of the individual through art. Lighting must serve this larger purpose, not just as a technical appendage, but as a devotional instrument—illuminating not just the stage, but the soul.

Endnotes:

ⁱ Maheswari, Nanda Kishore. *Natokar Kisu Kotha*, page 68

ⁱⁱ Barua, Debananda, edit. *Hemkosha*, (Guwahati, Hemkosha Prakshan, 2015) p.164

ⁱⁱⁱ Goswami, Utpal, Narayan. *Bhaonar Purbaranga: Vaividhya aru Vaicitrya (Dissertation, M.Phil, Guwahati University)*, page, 27

^{iv} Thakuriya, Ramcharan, Pathak, Dayanand, edit. *Natya Prasang*. page 82

^v Thakuriya, Ramcharan, Pathak, Dayanand, edit. *Natya Prasang*. page 83

^{vi} Thakuriya, Ramcharan, Pathak, Dayanand, edit. *NatyaPrasang*. page 83

^{vii} Thakuriya, Ramcharan, Pathak, Dayanand, edit. *NatyaPrasang*. page 83

^{viii} Thakuriya, Ramcharan, Pathak, Dayanand, edit. *NatyaPrasang*. page 83

^{ix} Thakuriya, Ramcharan, Pathak, Dayanand, edit. *NatyaPrasang*. page 83

^x Goswami, Utpal, Narayan. *Bhaonar Purbaranga: Vaividhya aru Vaicitrya (Dissertation, M.Phil, Guwahati University)*, page, 30

^{xi} Goswami, Utpal, Narayan. *Bhaonar Purbaranga: Vaividhyaaru Vaicitrya (Dissertation, M.Phil, Guwahati University)*, page, 28

^{xii} Barua, Debananda, edit. *Hemkosha*, (Guwahati, HemkoshaPrakshan, 2015) page. 666

^{xiii} Dev Goswami, Kesavananda. *Ankia Bhaona*. Page 78

^{xiv} Thakuriya, Ramcharan, Pathak, Dayanand, edit. *NatyaPrasang*. page 84

^{xv} Goswami, Utpal, Narayan. *Bhaonar Purbaranga: Vaividhyaaru Vaicitrya (Dissertation, M.Phil, Guwahati University)*, page, 30

^{xvi} Dev Goswami, Kesavananda. *Ankia Bhaona*. Page 78, 79

^{xvii} Dev Goswami, Kesavananda. *Ankia Bhaona*. Page 79

^{xviii} Thakuriya, Ramcharan, Pathak, Dayanand, edit. *Natya Prasang*. page 83

^{xix} Medhi Promud Chandra (edit). *Ragamancha*, page 82

^{xx} Bora, Hemchandra. *Shilpir Prithivi*, page 74

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